

E6.1 Validation Methodology and Performance Analysis Plan v1.0

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[6GENABLERS-DLT]
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**6G Networks Enabled through
Technology Driven Solutions
[6GENABLERS]**

**Programa de Universalización de
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Main Editor	Adriana Fernández-Fernández
Contributors	i2CAT
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List of Acronyms

6G	Sixth Generation
AF	Application Function
API	Application Programming Interface
CNF	Containerized Network Functions
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DID	Decentralized Identifier
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
E2E	End-to-End
ID	Identifier
K8s	Kubernetes
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine Learning
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
NS	Network Service
OS	Open Source
RAM	Random Access Memory
RAN	Radio Access Network
SC	Smart Contract
SCSC	Smart Contract State Composer
SD	Smart Discovery
SLA	Service Level Agreement
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VR	Virtual Reality
VSC	Vertical Service Consumer
VSP	Vertical Service Provider
VSV	Vertical Service Vendor
XR	eXtended Reality

Executive Summary

This document corresponds to the deliverable *E6.1 Validation Methodology and Performance Analysis Plan*, envisaged in the framework of the project 6GENABLERS-DLT (TSI-063000-2021-12). This deliverable outlines a comprehensive validation methodology and performance analysis plan for the 6GENABLERS-DLT project's Marketplace. Aligned with the objectives of Work Package 6, it contributes to the overall project's goal of deploying and validating a distributed telco Marketplace. The document covers the systematic approach to validation, detailed use case scenarios, performance analysis plan, and the deployment environment. In summary, Deliverable E6.1 serves as a crucial milestone in the 6GENABLERS-DLT project, providing a robust validation methodology and performance analysis plan for the innovative Marketplace. With a systematic approach, detailed use case scenarios, and a focus on key performance indicators, this document sets the stage for comprehensive validation exercises. The deployment environment insights and performance metrics offer a clear path for evaluating the Marketplace's capabilities in supporting multi-party collaboration within the dynamic landscape of 6G environments. As the project progresses, the methodologies outlined here will play a pivotal role in ensuring the successful realization and optimization of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. By emphasizing specific test cases, key performance indicators, and testbed setups, it lays the groundwork for effective validation exercises, ensuring the Marketplace's capability in facilitating multi-party collaboration within dynamic 6G environments.

1 Introduction

The core objective of the 6GENABLERS-DLT project is to establish a robust platform that empowers diverse stakeholders across geographical regions to trade a variety of telco resources. These resources encompass elements such as computing and radio infrastructure, network slices, Virtual Network Functions (VNFs), Containerized Network Functions (CNFs) and Network Services (NSs). The ultimate aim is to enable stakeholders to utilize these resources in creating and delivering 6G services.

To achieve this vision, the 6GENABLERS-DLT project is developing a sophisticated architecture for a decentralized marketplace, the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, with multiple sub-systems. This architecture includes systems such as Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLTs), Smart Contracts (SCs), Smart Discovery (SD) and Service Level Agreement (SLA) assurance mechanisms. These systems collectively facilitate the negotiation of contracts, reservation/leasing of various resources, and the lifecycle management of diverse resources within virtualization infrastructures for 6G. The 6GENABLERS Marketplace serves as the pivotal enabler for trading, chaining, and orchestrating provisioning actions across multiple administrative and technological domains.

Demonstrations and comprehensive validation of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace are slated to be carried out through a singular use case (UC), oriented to the establishment of multi-party real-time holographic communications as one of the most envisioned applications in 6G. This use case is designed to showcase the practical application of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace for ubiquitous resource trading and provisioning in the context of Extended Reality (XR) applications.

Details pertaining to the use case description and specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) originating from the different systems are outlined in deliverable E2.1 [1].

This document serves as the initial validation plan for the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. It provides insights into the defined test cases, use case scenarios and designated testbed, outlining how the 6GENABLERS Marketplace platform's components, developed in accordance with deliverables D3.1 [2], D4.1 [3] and D5.1 [4], will be deployed and validated. The testbed setup information establishes the baseline reference for conducting tests and demonstrating the capabilities of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace within a more realistic environment.

1.1 Document Scope and Objectives

This document, titled "E6.1 Validation Methodology and Performance Analysis Plan", plays a pivotal role in providing a structured and detailed approach to validating the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

The scope of this document encompasses the formulation of a comprehensive validation strategy for the 6GENABLERS-DLT project. The primary objectives are to define the validation goals, scope, and methodologies that will be employed to assess the functionality, performance, and adherence to identified KPIs.

The objectives detailed hereafter are intricately aligned with the deliverable's purpose. Through these objectives, this document aims to provide a clear roadmap for the validation activities, ensuring that the 6GENABLERS Marketplace aligns seamlessly with project objectives and successfully meets the requirements set forth in the use case.

- 1) Define Clear Validation Goals: Clearly articulate the overarching objectives of the validation process, focusing on ensuring the effectiveness and efficiency of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace within the context of the use case.
- 2) Establish Validation Scope: Outline the specific aspects and functionalities of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace that will be subject to validation, with a particular emphasis on the use case requirements.
- 3) Detail Validation Methodology: Elaborate on the approach, procedures, and methods that will be employed to validate the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. This includes defining test cases, scenarios, and performance metrics relevant to the use case.
- 4) Identify KPIs: Homogenize and measure KPIs associated with the 6GENABLERS Marketplace's objectives, ensuring alignment with project goals and the success criteria outlined in deliverables.
- 5) Establish Validation Environment: Describe the testbed infrastructure where the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, along with its underlying components, will be deployed for thorough validation.

In addition to these objectives, the document adheres to the requirements set forth in the project's description. It meticulously describes test cases for each use case scenario, highlighting pre-conditions, mechanisms for execution, involved actors, and measurement procedures for KPI evaluations. The methodology ensures a comprehensive coverage of all exercises required for the deployment of use cases and the planned measurement of targeted KPIs.

1.2 Relation to the Project's Activities

This document, corresponding to the initial outcome of Work Package 6 (P6), is intricately connected to the broader activities within this work package of the 6GENABLERS-DLT project. P6 is specifically dedicated to the validation of the smart marketplace derived from preceding work packages (P2-P5), emphasizing its functionality in facilitating multi-party holographic communications (holo-comms). The primary focus areas of the validation workflow include:

- Addition of Participants: Explore the integration of new marketplace participants, allowing them to function as trading entities in either a consumer or provider role.
- Holo-Comms Services: Demonstrate the on-demand announcement of holo-comms services, ensuring their compliance with specified SLAs.
- Purchase and Contract Settlement: Validate the processes involved in purchasing holo-comms services and settling contracts to commence service consumption.

- SLA Enforcement Monitoring: Implement monitoring mechanisms for SLA enforcement, including automated discovery of third-party infrastructure resources contributing to the overall holo-comms service.

This deliverable is the tangible outcome of the tasks performed under A6.1 within P6. Task A6.1, titled "Validation Methodology and Performance Analysis," is specifically designed to accomplish the following:

- Define Validation Methodology: Outline a comprehensive validation methodology that encompasses the exercises necessary for deploying use case scenarios over the DLT-anchored Smart Marketplace for 6G.
- Conduct Performance Analysis: Conduct a thorough performance analysis, evaluating the capabilities of the Marketplace platform based on technical KPIs outlined in P2. The assessment will be grounded in the context of the holographic communications service use case, serving as a validator for 6G verticals.

In essence, this deliverable serves as a crucial link in the validation efforts within P6, providing a strategic plan for the validation of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace while emphasizing the significance of the holographic communications service as a key 6G vertical validator.

1.3 Structure of the Document

The structure of this document is meticulously organized to offer a comprehensive understanding of the validation methodology and performance analysis plan for the 6GENABLERS-DLT project. The document unfolds as follows:

- Section 1: The introductory section provides an overview of the document, presenting the document's overview, objectives, and relation to project activities.
- Section 2: This section elucidates the validation methodology outlining the specific objectives and scope that govern the validation exercises, and detailing the systematic approach adopted for the validation.
- Section 3: Delving into the heart of the document, this section focuses on use case validation. It describes the individual test cases for the designated use case scenarios.
- Section 4: This section navigates through the performance analysis plan, listing the KPIs associated with the capabilities and performance of the core functional systems within the 6GENABLERS-DLT project.
- Section 5: This section elaborates on the deployment and validation environment, elucidating the testbed setup required to host the Marketplace platform, ensuring a multi-party network for validation purposes.
- Section 6: The document culminates in a concluding section, encapsulating essential takeaways derived from the validation methodology and performance analysis.
- Section 7: The final section serves as a repository of references, providing the list of citations that support the information presented throughout the document.

2 Validation Methodology

The validation methodology for the 6GENABLERS-DLT is designed to thoroughly assess the platform capabilities in facilitating multi-party real-time holographic communications. This involves testing various scenarios and operations related to the trading and provisioning of different telco assets. The operations to be validated encompass stakeholder onboarding, offer creation, offer discovery, order creation, order deployment, SLA monitoring and evaluation, and SLA violation notification and registration. This section outlines the systematic approach, objectives, and procedures undertaken to validate the functionalities inherent to the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

2.1 Validation Objectives and Scope

The validation objectives for the 6GENABLERS-DLT are instrumental in ensuring that the platform aligns seamlessly with the overarching goals of the project. These objectives serve as a comprehensive guide to validate the marketplace's capabilities in fostering multi-party collaboration, resource sharing, and efficient trading within the dynamic landscape of 6G environments.

- **Platform Functionality Alignment:** Validate the alignment of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace with the overall objectives of the 6GENABLERS-DLT project. Ensure that the marketplace functionalities are designed to meet the project's goals for multi-party collaboration and resource sharing.
- **Functional Features Assessment:** Evaluate the functional features of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. Examine the platform's ability to support multi-party collaboration, resource sharing, and efficient trading in the 6G environment.
- **Stakeholder Interaction and Workflow Validation:** Validate stakeholder interactions and the effectiveness of workflows within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. Confirm that the platform provides a user-friendly environment for stakeholders, and workflows are well-designed to facilitate seamless resource sharing and collaboration.
- **Functional Systems Enablement:** Establish and validate the capabilities of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace enabled by DLTs, Smart Contracts, Smart Discovery, and SLA Assurance. Verify that the Marketplace effectively leverages these technological pillars to enhance transparency, security, and efficiency in resource trading.
- **KPIs Homogenization and Measurement:** Refine and consolidate identified KPIs to ensure they reflect the core functionalities and success criteria of the decentralized platform. Measure and validate the KPIs to assess the platform's performance against predefined objectives.
- **Realistic Validation Scenarios:** Validate the 6GENABLERS Marketplace in realistic scenarios that showcase its capabilities in dynamic 6G environments. Confirm that the chosen scenarios accurately represent the operational conditions and challenges faced by the Marketplace.

In summary, the defined scope serves as a comprehensive framework to evaluate and confirm the effectiveness of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. It encompasses a comprehensive assessment of its functional features, stakeholder interactions, integration with core functional systems, measurement of KPIs, and scenario-based

testing. By defining the scope, we aim to thoroughly analyze the platform's capabilities, ensuring it meets the diverse requirements of multi-party collaboration and resource trading within the dynamic framework of 6G environments.

2.2 Validation Approach and Procedures

The validation of the 6GENABLERS-DLT project follows a systematic approach to ensure coherence, alignment, and effectiveness in the evaluation process. This systematic methodology unfolds in distinct steps, as depicted in Figure 2-1, each building upon the preceding phase, ultimately leading to the comprehensive validation of use cases and platform functionalities.

Figure 2-1 Validation Methodology

The systematic validation approach commences with the foundational elements established in the initial definition of use case and KPIs documented in E2.1. This phase sets the stage, providing a clear roadmap that serves as the guiding framework for subsequent validation activities.

Building on the initial definition, the next pivotal step involves the development of a comprehensive validation methodology and performance analysis plan, which is presented in this deliverable. This phase includes the elicitation of specific test cases, ensuring that they intricately correspond to the scenario-based testing approach envisioned in the project.

With the validation plan in place, a parallel line of work involves the implementation of the platform prototypes. This implementation is carefully aligned with the expectations outlined in the evaluation plan. The prototypes serve as a tangible representation of the envisioned platform, allowing for iterative feedback loops to refine its features and functionalities.

The conclusive step marks the final validation and performance analysis, to be reported in E6.2, characterized by the final report of actual measurement and experimentation. This phase serves to validate the deployment of use case scenarios against the initial definition, ensuring that the envisioned scenarios align with real-world applications. The assessment also involves a comprehensive evaluation of platform functionalities, validating their alignment with predefined KPIs. Simultaneously, a detailed performance evaluation is conducted to gauge the efficiency and effectiveness of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

To implement this validation approach, the following procedures have been established:

- Define and refine the validation methodology and performance analysis plan.
- Ensure that the defined test cases align with the scenario-based testing approach, reflecting the complexity and diversity of real-world use cases.
- Align the development of the platform prototypes with the expectations set forth in the validation plan.
- Facilitate iterative feedback loops to refine the prototype, ensuring that it accurately represents the envisioned platform functionalities.
- Execute the measurement and experimentation processes according to the defined plan.
- Validate the deployment of use case scenarios against the initial use case definition in E2.1 and E6.1, ensuring their alignment with real-world scenarios.
- Assess platform functionalities comprehensively, ensuring that they align with predefined KPIs.
- Conduct a detailed performance evaluation to gauge the platform's efficiency and effectiveness in diverse operational scenarios.

This systematic approach and associated procedures ensure a methodical and coherent progression from the inception of use cases to the final validation, contributing to the robustness and readiness of the 6GENABLERS-DLT project for dynamic multi-party collaborations within 6G environments.

3 Use Case Validation

HoloMIT is a modular end-to-end platform to enable multiuser holographic communication services, using realistic and volumetric user representations, captured in real-time using affordable and off-the-shelf sensors [5][6]. Its applicability spans entertainment, but it can provide multiple benefits in a variety of relevant sectors, such as multiuser meetings [5], participation in virtual events [6], or even virtual tourism [7]. This represents the vertical service to be validated in 6GENABLERS-DLT as a potential dominant medium for remote communication, social interaction and collaboration in the near future.

Since its conception, HoloMIT adopted a classical client-server architecture [5][6], with native clients to be installed on each client devices, and a set of monolithic and statically deployed cloud-based functions to mainly: (i) host and provide the Virtual Reality (VR) content and scenarios (denoted as XR Content Servers); and to (ii) manage the multiuser sessions and associated communications (denoted as XR Orchestrator).

In recent years, the advent of 5G-advanced networks and computing continuum paradigms has opened the door to leveraging edge computing as well as secured and smart orchestration strategies (e.g. [8]) to overcome current interoperability, scalability, and cost barriers that the mass adoption of XR services, such as those based on HoloMIT, is currently facing. In this context, recent works have shown that the adoption of cloud-assisted strategies for media processing can contribute to lowering the computation and bandwidth requirements on the client side (e.g. [8], [9], [10]).

HoloMIT is being evolved in this direction, and two main in-network Application Functions (AFs) are currently being incorporated into the platform:

- **VNF1: Edge-assisted Communications Function.** It consists of a combination of virtualized managers and services to perform essential media processing and communication steps in the User Plane, like stream forwarding, mixing and transcoding. By using VNF1, it is then possible to strategically instantiate these functions as required on the most adequate edge resources, for every active HoloMIT session.
- **VNF2: Remote Rendering Function.** In HoloMIT sessions, each native client needs to receive a set of volumetric and 2D video streams, in conjunction to other multimodal streams (e.g. audio, textual info, interaction events...), decode them, and compose a coherent scene with fast granularity. This results in stringent bandwidth and processing requirements, even if VNF1 has been activated for the associated session. VNF2 consists of a remote / edge renderer module, which in essence takes the role of a 'surrogate' native client on the edge, which additionally provides a personalized rendered (2D or 360°) video stream to more lightweight clients in HoloMIT sessions, like a web player on a mobile device or XR headset.

Regarding clients, the full-fledged native player needs to be distributed to interested customers/clients, which is labelled as VNF3 in this document. In turns, when considering the lightweight scheme enabled by VNF2, a web-based consumption and interaction endpoint is required on the client side, which is referred to as VNF4.

The resulting high-level architecture of the HoloMIT application with the different functions introduced above is sketched in Figure 3-1.

Figure 3-1 High-level Overview of the HoloMIT Application

6GENABLERS-DLT will demonstrate their main outcomes by considering the full-fledged offering of the HoloMIT application, and particularly the trusted acquisition of VNFs (such as VNF2) and the provisioning of the overall application distributed over edge and cloud infrastructure resources. Note, that although it can be perfectly accommodated within the scope of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, the trading of extreme edge / UEs resources is not foreseen in the planned validation scenarios.

3.1 Test Cases

This subsection outlines a comprehensive set of test cases designed to systematically evaluate the performance and functionality of key operations within the 6GENABLERS-DLT project. Each test case is meticulously crafted to assess specific aspects of the platform, ensuring robustness, security, and efficiency in the diverse range of business interactions it facilitates. Through these test cases, we aim to validate and optimize critical functionalities, providing a detailed examination of stakeholder onboarding, offer creation, offer discovery, order creation, order deployment, SLA monitoring and evaluation, as well as SLA violation handling. The ensuing descriptions delve into each test case, elucidating the procedural details, involved stakeholders, platform components, and anticipated outcomes, contributing to a thorough understanding of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace system's capabilities.

3.1.1 Stakeholder Onboarding

The stakeholder onboarding process serves as the foundational step for integrating new participants into the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, representing the crucial initiation phase required for joining the platform. This essential operation involves the generation and

secure storage of unique identifiers and credentials within the distributed ledger. These identifiers and credentials play a pivotal role in establishing a secure and verifiable foundation for every subsequent business interaction between the stakeholder and the platform.

During onboarding, a record of the stakeholder's identity and authentication details is created and securely stored in the ledger. This ensures a robust and tamper-proof mechanism, fostering a trusted environment for all engagements within the Marketplace. The generated credentials not only authenticate the stakeholder but also authorize their access to specific functionalities and services within the platform.

By formalizing the onboarding process, the 6GENABLERS Marketplace establishes a resilient framework that enhances security, transparency, and accountability. The recorded information not only facilitates seamless interactions between stakeholders and the platform but also contributes to the overall integrity and reliability of the distributed ledger. Table 3-1 details the stakeholder onboarding test case, shedding light on its procedural aspects, involved platform components, and anticipated outcomes.

Table 3-1 Stakeholder Onboarding Test Case

Name	Stakeholder Onboarding
Description	Obtain Decentralized Identifier (DID) and permissions for platform access and for adding, updating, and retrieving offers and orders, through the DLT-based distributed identity service.
Platform Components	Identity API, Identity DLT
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Marketplace has been initialized. • Administrators' peers exist with the authority to grant all permissions to new network participants. • Stakeholder has deployed their instance of the Marketplace platform.
Sequence Workflow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Stakeholder submits a request to join the Marketplace. 2. Governance Board (Marketplace Admins) reviews onboarding request, employing an approval mechanism. 3. Upon approval, Marketplace Admins provide the Stakeholder with a DID and credentials for decentralized Marketplace operations.
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder gains the ability to advertise/consume telco assets based on their assigned roles and permissions.

3.1.2 Offer Creation

The process of creating an offer marks a pivotal step where stakeholders showcase their telco assets on the Marketplace. In essence, offers encapsulate both the technical specifications of the resources available for trade and crucial business-related details, including pricing structures and SLAs. This comprehensive information serves as a comprehensive representation of the offered resource, enabling potential consumers to make informed decisions.

Through the dynamic functionality of the Trading DLT, offers seamlessly propagate across various domains within the decentralized Marketplace. This mechanism ensures that stakeholders' offerings reach a diverse audience, fostering collaboration and resource exchange across the entire ecosystem. Table 3-2 details the offer creation test

case, shedding light on its procedural aspects, involved platform components, and anticipated outcomes.

Table 3-2 Offer Creation Test Case

Name	Offer Creation
Description	Make network assets available on the Marketplace
Platform Components	SCSC, Offering API, Trading DLT, Identity API, Identity DLT, Smart Discovery Application, Data Bus, Broker Logic for Resource Control
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Completion of the Stakeholder Onboarding Test Case for the provider. • Provider stakeholder owns the offered asset and possesses required offer information (tech specs, price, SLA, etc.)
Sequence Workflow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Stakeholder requests to register a network offer using their stakeholder DID, providing relevant information (location, tech specs, price, SLA, etc.). 2. Marketplace platform verifies stakeholder identity, generates a new DID for the offer, classifies the offer based on pre-computed clusters, and verifies asset availability in the provider domain. 3. Marketplace platform responds to the stakeholder with the offer DID if properly registered, or an error if an issue occurs. 4. The offer is disseminated to all parties of the Marketplace.
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offer propagates cross-domain and is available in all distributed instances of the Marketplace for discovery and purchase. • Offer information stored in the ledger includes the generated DID and the cluster to which it has been classified.

3.1.3 Offer Discovery

The robust capability of offer discovery empowers stakeholders, with a special focus on those acting as consumers looking for a compelling offer, to seamlessly and effectively pinpoint existing offers within the dynamic 6GENABLERS Marketplace that precisely match their unique requirements. This pivotal operation serves as a gateway to a user-friendly and highly streamlined process, providing stakeholders with an intuitive and efficient means to explore and identify telco assets tailored to their specific needs.

The offer discovery process encapsulates a sophisticated mechanism designed to enhance the overall user experience within the Marketplace. By intelligently discerning and presenting telco assets that align with stakeholders' requirements, this operation acts as a catalyst for informed decision-making. Stakeholders can navigate the expansive offerings available within the decentralized ecosystem, facilitating a more agile and responsive approach to fulfilling their needs.

This operation is not merely about discovering offers; it's about providing stakeholders with a personalized and tailored experience, fostering an environment where stakeholders can effortlessly explore and identify telco assets that precisely meet their discovery criteria. Table 3-3 details the offer discovery test case, shedding light on its procedural aspects, involved platform components, and anticipated outcomes.

Table 3-3 Offer Discovery Test Case

Name	Offer Discovery
Description	Discover existing offers that align with specific user requirements
Platform Components	SCSC, Smart Discovery Application, Offering API, Trading DLT

Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Completion of the Stakeholder Onboarding Test Case for the consumer. • Offers available in the Marketplace meeting the consumer's expectations. • Consumer possesses envisioned offer information (category, etc.).
Sequence Workflow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Consumer stakeholder submits a discovery request in the form of an intent, containing their expectations. 2. Marketplace platform discerns the received intent and determines the corresponding cluster of offers that responds to the expressed needs. 3. Corresponding offers available at the Trading DLT are returned to the Stakeholder.
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder selects the most convenient offer and uses it to compose the payload for creating an order.

3.1.4 Order Creation

The creation of orders stands as a pivotal operation, offering a seamless pathway for stakeholders to effortlessly procure telco assets from the diverse array of offerings within the expansive 6GENABLERS Marketplace. In the consumer domain, once published offers have been discovered, stakeholders proceed to seamlessly transition from the selection phase to the initiation of the formal acquisition process through the order creation operation.

Following the selection of a specific offer, consumers submit a well-defined request, providing essential details such as the corresponding offer. By managing the creation of orders, the platform not only facilitates the acquisition of telco assets but also ensures that the entire process is user-friendly, efficient, and secure.

Table 3-4 details the order creation test case, shedding light on its procedural aspects, involved platform components, and anticipated outcomes.

Table 3-4 Order Creation Test Case

Name	Order Creation
Description	Acquire telco assets from the Marketplace
Platform Components	SCSC, Order API, Trading DLT, Identity API, Identity DLT
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Completion of the Offer Discovery Test Case. • Consumer stakeholder selects an offer for purchase. • Selected offer remains available at the Marketplace.
Sequence Workflow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Stakeholder requests to register a network order using their stakeholder DID, specifying the selected offer. 2. Marketplace platform verifies stakeholder identity and generates a new DID for the order. 3. Marketplace platform responds to the stakeholder with the order DID if properly registered, or an error if an issue occurs. 4. The order is disseminated to involved parties of the Marketplace.
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Order propagates cross-domain and is available in the distributed Marketplace instances of involved parties (providers and consumer). • Order information stored in the ledger includes the generated DID.

3.1.5 Order Deployment

Following the successful placement of an order, the consumer stakeholder is entitled to request the provision of the acquired telco asset. The deployment of orders plays a pivotal role in the seamless execution of telco asset acquisition within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. It is designed to orchestrate the deployment and provisioning of acquired telco assets, ensuring a smooth transition from the purchase phase to the active use of the resources.

The deployment of orders signifies more than a mere technical process; it represents the bridge between intention and realization in the dynamic landscape of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. It is at this juncture that the platform transforms the stakeholder's request into actionable deployment steps, ensuring the timely and efficient provisioning of the telco asset for their deployment and utilization. Table 3-5 details the order deployment test case, shedding light on its procedural aspects, involved platform components, and anticipated outcomes.

Table 3-5 Order Deployment Test Case

Name	Order Deployment
Description	Deploy and provision acquired telco asset
Platform Components	SCSC, SC State API, Trading DLT, Identity API, Identity DLT, Data Bus, Broker Logic for Resource Control
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Completion of the Order Creation Test Case. • Purchased asset remains available at the provider domain.
Sequence Workflow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Stakeholder requests to deploy the acquired telco resource using their stakeholder DID, specifying the corresponding order. 2. Marketplace platform verifies stakeholder identity and generates a new DID for the SC state, representing deployment actions and post-purchase follow-up. 3. Marketplace platform responds to the stakeholder with the SC state DID if properly registered, or an error if an issue occurs. 4. The SC state is disseminated to involved parties of the Marketplace. 5. Marketplace platform at the provider domain proceeds with the verification of availability and the deployment of the traded asset. 6. Upon deployment, status updates are propagated through the ledger back to the buyer's domain.
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marketplace platform actively monitors provisioned resource.

3.1.6 SLA Monitoring and Evaluation

The monitoring and evaluation of SLA is a critical operation within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, dedicated to the ongoing oversight and assessment of deployed telco assets to ensure adherence to SLA terms. This operation is designed to systematically monitor the performance of deployed resources and evaluate their compliance with the predefined SLA, thereby guaranteeing the quality and reliability of telco services.

By systematically examining the performance metrics against established SLA thresholds, this operation not only identifies deviations but also enables proactive interventions to address potential issues, ensuring that the telco services consistently meet and exceed the expectations of stakeholders. Table 3-6 details the SLA monitoring

and evaluation test case, shedding light on its procedural aspects, involved platform components, and anticipated outcomes.

Table 3-6 SLA Monitoring and Evaluation Test Case

Name	SLA Monitoring and Evaluation
Description	Monitor deployed telco asset and evaluate SLA compliance
Platform Components	Broker Logic for Resource Control, Data Bus, Monitoring and Network Analytics Aggregator, Data Lake, Proactive SLA Monitoring
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Completion of the Order Deployment Test Case • SLA terms related to the traded asset are published in the Data Lake.
Sequence Workflow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Once the deployment has been successfully completed, and during the lifetime of the contract, the Marketplace Platform monitors periodically the deployed resource. 2. All the relevant metrics according to the corresponding SLA are fetched, aggregated, and stored locally. 3. Marketplace platform evaluates the received metrics, comparing them with the threshold values defined in the SLA. 4. Marketplace platform assesses whether the observed performance complies with the agreed SLA, by predicting or detecting any violation to these terms.
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alerts or alarms could be generated based on the evaluation outcomes.

3.1.7 SLA Violation Notification and Registration

The process of notifying and registering SLA violations stands as a pivotal and decisive operation within the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. Tailored to address potential or actual violations of SLA, this operation is intricately designed to swiftly initiate actions that remediate issues and uphold the agreed-upon service standards. It involves the use of messages to notify stakeholders of SLA breaches, concurrently committing these violations to the ledger for comprehensive documentation and visibility.

The dual nature of notification and registration serves a dual purpose – it communicates the breach to relevant stakeholders for timely remediation while also providing a transparent, ledger-based record of the violation. Table 3-7 details the SLA violation notification and registration test case, shedding light on its procedural aspects, involved platform components, and anticipated outcomes.

Table 3-7 SLA Violation Notification and Registration Test Case

Name	SLA Violation Notification and Registration
Description	Notification of predicted or detected SLA violation and its registration in the ledger
Platform Components	Proactive SLA Monitoring, Data Bus, SCSC, SC State API, Trading DLT
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Completion of the SLA Monitoring and Evaluation Test Case • Performance of deployed telco asset starts to deteriorate.
Sequence Workflow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) During the lifetime of the contract and monitoring of the resources, two sub-scenarios related to SLA verification are supported: 2) SLA violation prediction <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Marketplace platform predicts a potential SLA violation based on the observed performance deterioration. b. Marketplace platform announces this event using an SLA alert, which becomes available at the provider domain.

	3) SLA violation detection <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Assuming the situation continues and becomes an SLA violation, this is promptly detected by the Marketplace platform. b. After detecting an SLA violation, an SLA alarm is generated, which is registered at the ledger becoming available at the involved domains.
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contract termination and tear-down at the end of the lease period, releasing resources back making them available for leasing again.

3.2 Use Case Scenarios

This section provides a detailed exploration of a diverse array of use case scenarios that exemplify the practical application of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, where stakeholders seamlessly engage to fulfil operational needs through transparent and efficient resource trading. These scenarios are carefully crafted to reflect real-world, multi-party collaboration within dynamic 6G environments between service providers, resource providers, and operators in order to harness the collective power of resources.

The scenarios presented in this section play a dual role: they are designed to address the KPIs initially defined in E2.1 [1], and further identified in Section 4, while intricately simulating the diverse operational facets of a Vertical Service Provider (VSP) as provider of the HoloMIT application. Specifically, these scenarios emulate the VSPs' utilization of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace to procure essential resources for delivering a holistic service package to their customers.

3.2.1 Virtualized Functions Trading

The Virtualized Functions Trading scenario represents the initial acquisition of VNF resources to meet specific operational requirements for the composition of the overarching HoloMIT application. Different combinations are possible in this scenario, given the modular architecture of the HoloMIT service. For instance, the VSP may acquire VNF1+VNF3 for the native client, and VNF2+VNF4 for remote rendering and lightweight web-based player to offer XR services for both native and web-based clients.

3.2.1.1 Involved Stakeholders and Platform Components

In this scenario, the VSP, acting as consumer, leases a VNF from a resource provider, in this case a VNF Vendor (VSV). This represents the base scenario for the use case, as it demonstrates marketplace utilization to support software resource trading establishment backed by a smart contract bi-lateral agreement and associated SLAs. The stakeholders and platform components involved in this scenario are summarized in Table 3-8.

Table 3-8 Stakeholders and Platform Components, Scenario 1

Stakeholder – Role	Stakeholder Description	Platform components	Network Infrastructure
VSV – Provider	Vendor of the virtualized functions offer. As a provider, their primary role involves offering virtualized functions for trading, making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identity API • Identity DLT • SCSC • Offering API • Trading DLT 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Registry to host traded virtualized functions

	their resources available for consumption by other stakeholders.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smart Discovery App • Data Bus • Broker Logic for Resource Controller 	
VSP – Consumer	Buyer of the virtualized functions offer. Their role involves identifying, selecting, and acquiring virtualized functions from providers like the VSV to meet specific operational needs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identity API • Identity DLT • SCSC • Order API • Trading DLT • Smart Discovery App • Offering API 	N/A

Table 3-9 outlines the main details of the resource being traded in this scenario. In this case, the offer consists of virtualized functions.

Table 3-9 Resources Overview, Scenario 1

Asset	Technical Specification	Business Terms	SLA Terms
Virtualized Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • vCPU Requirements • RAM Requirements • Storage Requirements • Type of Function 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pricing model (e.g. flat, tiered, subscription) [1] • Software license model (e.g. perpetual, open source (OS), recurring) [1] 	Service level offered in accordance with the virtualized function type (e.g. number of supported concurrent sessions)

3.2.1.2 Test Plan

For the validation of this scenario, the following test cases are relevant.

- Stakeholder Onboarding: The deployment of the Marketplace instance and the registration as participants for the VSV and the VSP.
- Offer Creation: The VSV creates a detailed offer for the virtualized function within the Marketplace, specifying technical details, business, and SLA terms.
- Offer Discovery: The VSP identifies the relevant virtualized function as a suitable match for their needs for its integration into the HoloMIT application.
- Order Creation: The VSP initiates the acquisition process by creating an order for the relevant virtualized function, formalizing the commercial transaction.

Note that the rest of test cases are not under the scope of this scenario, since the acquired virtualized functions will be deployed as part of the overall HoloMIT application deployment (see Section 3.2.4).

3.2.2 Cloud Resource Trading and Provisioning

In the Cloud Resource Trading and Provisioning scenario, the focus is on the acquisition of a cloud resource by the VSP and its subsequent provisioning. This cloud resource serves a specific purpose, such as hosting HoloMIT's XR Content Server(s) and XR Orchestrator (i.e. the central entity that governs the service logic). The acquired cloud resource becomes a critical component for enabling the desired functionalities and services offered by the HoloMIT application. It's important to note that the onboarding of application artifacts to this cloud resource is integral to the scenario, although the specifics of this onboarding process fall outside the scope of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

3.2.2.1 Involved Stakeholders and Platform Components

In this scenario, the VSP, acting as consumer, leases a cloud resource from a resource provider, in this case an Infrastructure Provider. This scenario demonstrates marketplace utilization to support computing infrastructure resource trading backed by a smart contract bi-lateral agreement and associated SLAs. The stakeholders and platform components involved in this scenario are summarized in Table 3-10.

Table 3-10 Stakeholders and Platform Components, Scenario 2

Stakeholder – Role	Stakeholder Description	Platform components	Network Infrastructure
Infrastructure Provider – Provider	Vendor of the cloud resource offer. As a provider of cloud resources, their primary function is to offer infrastructure capabilities for hosting applications of consumers like the VSP.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identity API • Identity DLT • SCSC • Offering API • Trading DLT • Smart Discovery App • Data Bus • Broker Logic for Resource Controller • SC State API • Monitoring and Network Analytics Aggregator • Data Lake • Proactive SLA Monitoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtualized cloud infrastructure • Management entities of the offered cloud infrastructure (e.g. i2Slicer + OpenStack / k8s) • Monitoring stack (e.g. Prometheus)
VSP – Consumer	Buyer of the cloud resource offer. As a consumer, their objective is to lease a cloud resource from infrastructure providers to meet specific operational requirements, such as hosting the cloud-based functions of HoloMIT.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SCSC • Order API • Trading DLT • Identity API • Identity DLT • Smart Discovery App • Offering API • SC State API • Data Bus 	N/A

Table 3-11 outlines the main details of the resource being traded in this scenario. In this case, the offer consists of a cloud resource.

Table 3-11 Resources Overview, Scenario 2

Asset	Technical Specification	Business Terms	SLA Terms
Cloud Resource	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CPU • Memory (RAM) • Storage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pricing model (e.g. flat, subscription) [1] 	Service level offered (e.g. availability)

3.2.2.2 Test Plan

For the validation of this scenario, the following test cases are relevant. It is assumed that the previous scenario has been performed, and therefore the VSP is already onboard on the platform.

- Stakeholder Onboarding: The deployment of the Marketplace instance and the registration as participant for the Infrastructure Provider.

- Offer Creation: The Infrastructure Provider creates a detailed offer for the cloud resource within the Marketplace, specifying technical details, business, and SLA terms.
- Offer Discovery: The VSP identifies the relevant cloud resource as a suitable match for their needs for the deployment of cloud-based application functions.
- Order Creation: The VSP initiates the acquisition process by creating an order for the relevant cloud resource, formalizing the commercial transaction.
- Order Deployment: The VSP requests the deployment of the acquired cloud resource, triggering the provisioning of the purchased cloud infrastructure capacity at the Infrastructure Provider domain.
- SLA Monitoring and Evaluation: The provisioned cloud resource is continuously monitored at the Infrastructure Provider domain to assess whether the observed performance aligns with the agreed upon SLA terms.
- SLA Violation Notification and Registration: The ongoing SLA monitoring reveals a performance deviation, which is registered in the ledger and notified to the Infrastructure Provider and the VSP.

3.2.3 Network Slice Trading and Provisioning

In the Network Slice Trading and Provisioning scenario, the focus is on the acquisition of a network slice by the VSP. This comprehensive network slice encompasses Radio Access Network (RAN), core, and edge capabilities, strategically located to align with the VSP's area of interest, typically corresponding to the envisioned point of presence for the XR service. The dynamic nature of this scenario enables the allocation of the network slice based on awareness of active clients in each session, ensuring the efficient fulfilment of their specific demands.

3.2.3.1 Involved Stakeholders and Platform Components

In this scenario, the VSP, acting as consumer, leases a network slice from a resource provider, in this case a Mobile Network Operator (MNO). This scenario demonstrates marketplace utilization to support network resource trading backed by a smart contract bi-lateral agreement and associated SLAs. The stakeholders and platform components involved in this scenario are summarized in Table 3-12.

Table 3-12 Stakeholders and Platform Components, Scenario 3

Stakeholder – Role	Stakeholder Description	Platform components	Network Infrastructure
MNO – Provider	Vendor of the network slice offer. This provider offers network slices to fulfill the VSP's requirements, providing RAN, core, and edge capabilities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identity API • Identity DLT • SCSC • Offering API • Trading DLT • Smart Discovery App • Data Bus • Broker Logic for Resource Controller • SC State API • Monitoring and Network Analytics Aggregator • Data Lake • Proactive SLA Monitoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtualized infrastructure and functions for the different slice segments (RAN, core, edge) • Management entities of the offered slice segments (e.g. i2Slicer + OpenStack / k8s) • Monitoring stack (e.g. Prometheus)

VSP – Consumer	Buyer of the network slice offer. Their purpose is to acquire a network slice tailored to the demands of XR service sessions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SCSC • Order API • Trading DLT • Identity API • Identity DLT • Smart Discovery App • Offering API • SC State API • Data Bus 	N/A
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Table 3-13 outlines the main details of the resource being traded in this scenario. In this case, the offer consists of a network slice.

Table 3-13 Resources Overview, Scenario 3

Asset	Technical Specification	Business Terms	SLA Terms
Network Slice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maximum downlink throughput • Maximum uplink throughput • Isolation level • Data network access • Access technology • Area of service • Radio spectrum 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pricing model (e.g. flat, subscription) [1] 	Service level offered (e.g. availability and reliability)

3.2.3.2 Test Plan

For the validation of this scenario, the following test cases are relevant. It is assumed that the previous scenarios have been performed, and therefore the VSP is already onboard on the platform.

- Stakeholder Onboarding: The deployment of the Marketplace instance and the registration as participant for the MNO.
- Offer Creation: The MNO creates a detailed offer for the network slice within the Marketplace, specifying technical details, business, and SLA terms.
- Offer Discovery: The VSP identifies the relevant network slice as a suitable match for their needs tailored to the demands of XR service sessions.
- Order Creation: The VSP initiates the acquisition process by creating an order for the relevant network slice, formalizing the commercial transaction.
- Order Deployment: The VSP requests the deployment of the acquired network slice, triggering the provisioning of the purchased RAN, core and edge capabilities at the MNO domain.
- SLA Monitoring and Evaluation: The provisioned network slice is continuously monitored at the MNO domain to assess whether the observed performance aligns with the agreed upon SLA terms.
- SLA Violation Notification and Registration: The ongoing SLA monitoring reveals a performance deviation, which is registered in the ledger and notified to the MNO and the VSP.

3.2.4 Network Service Trading and Provisioning

In the Network Service Trading and Provisioning scenario, the focus is on the acquisition and deployment of the HoloMIT application requested by the Vertical Service Consumer (VSC). The challenge lies in ensuring the deployment of the cloud-based functions on the previously purchased cloud resource, while deploying the remaining virtualized functions on the edge compute resource of the allocated network slice. Furthermore, the scenario will be extended to involve more than one domain, emulating multiple sessions of at least two concurrent users in different locations, introducing additional complexities to the deployment process.

3.2.4.1 Involved Stakeholders and Platform Components

In this scenario, the VSC, acting as consumer, purchases the HoloMIT service from a provider, in this case the VSP. This scenario demonstrates marketplace utilization to support network/vertical service trading backed by a smart contract bi-lateral agreement and associated SLAs. The stakeholders and platform components involved in this scenario are summarized in Table 3-14.

Table 3-14 Stakeholders and Platform Components, Scenario 4

Stakeholder – Role	Stakeholder Description	Platform components	Network Infrastructure
VSP – Provider	Vendor of the vertical network service offer. This provider offers XR services to fulfill the VSC's expectations of enjoying remote and immersive communication.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identity API • Identity DLT • SCSC • Offering API • Trading DLT • Smart Discovery App • Data Bus • Broker Logic for Resource Controller • SC State API • Monitoring and Network Analytics Aggregator • Data Lake • Proactive SLA Monitoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vertical network service (HoloMIT) • Purchased network and infrastructure resources at the Infrastructure Provider and MNO domains. • Monitoring stack at the Infrastructure Provider and MNO domains (e.g. Prometheus)
VSC – Consumer	Buyer of the vertical network service offer. Their purpose is to acquire an XR service for establishing for instance immersive multiuser virtual meetings.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SCSC • Order API • Trading DLT • Identity API • Identity DLT • Smart Discovery App • Offering API • SC State API • Data Bus 	N/A

Table 3-15 outlines the main details of the resource being traded in this scenario. In this case, the offer consists of a vertical network service.

Table 3-15 Resources Overview, Scenario 4

Asset	Technical Specification	Business Terms	SLA Terms
Network Service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • vCPU Requirements • RAM Requirements • Storage Requirements • Type of Service 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pricing model (e.g. flat, tiered, subscription) [1] • Software license model (e.g. perpetual, open source (OS), recurring) [1] 	Service level offered in accordance with the service type (e.g. number of supported concurrent sessions)

3.2.4.2 Test Plan

For the validation of this scenario, the following test cases are relevant. It is assumed that the previous scenarios have been performed, and therefore the VSP is already onboard on the platform.

- Stakeholder Onboarding: The deployment of the Marketplace instance and the registration as participant for the VSC.
- Offer Creation: The VSP creates a detailed offer for the network service within the Marketplace, specifying technical details, business, and SLA terms.
- Offer Discovery: The VSC identifies the relevant network service as a suitable match for their needs for establishing for instance immersive multiuser virtual meetings.
- Order Creation: The VSC initiates the acquisition process by creating an order for the relevant network service, formalizing the commercial transaction.
- Order Deployment: The VSC requests the deployment of the acquired network service, triggering the provisioning of the purchased network service at the cloud and edge capabilities at the Infrastructure Provider and MNO domains, respectively.
- SLA Monitoring and Evaluation: The provisioned network service is continuously monitored at the domains involved in the deployed service to assess whether the observed performance aligns with the agreed upon SLA terms.
- SLA Violation Notification and Registration: The ongoing SLA monitoring reveals a performance deviation, which is registered in the ledger and notified to the VSP and the VSC.

4 Performance Analysis Plan

In the pursuit of validating the functionalities within the 6GENABLERS-DLT project, specific KPIs have been identified, as documented in E2.1 [1]. These KPIs play a critical role in assessing the capabilities and performance of the four core functional systems, namely DLT, Smart Contracts, Smart Discovery, and SLA Assurance, which are referenced in the KPI ID, alongside their implemented prototypes. The majority of these KPIs are intricately tied to the technologies and implementation decisions guiding the development of platform components.

Identified KPIs are not solely dependent on specific test scenarios but rather reflect the overall performance of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. Nonetheless, certain KPIs in the 6GENABLERS-DLT project have an impact on how use case tests are defined and how the testbed is equipped to align with the metric set.

By categorizing KPIs into Platform Capabilities and Use Case Validation, this performance analysis plan aims to provide clarity and homogeneity in assessing the overall performance of the 6GENABLERS-DLT platform and its specific alignment with real-world use case scenarios. The following subsections delve deeper into each category, offering a comprehensive overview of the KPIs and their respective implications on the project validation.

4.1 Platform Capabilities KPIs

The platform capabilities KPIs, derived from E2.1 [1], focus on assessing the overall performance of the 6GENABLERS-DLT platform without direct linkage to specific UC scenarios. These KPIs, grouped in Table 4-1, provide insights into the fundamental capabilities and efficiency of the core systems, offering a holistic view of the platform's prowess.

Table 4-1 Platform Capabilities KPIs

ID	Description	Evaluation Criteria
DLT System		
DLT-KPI-1	Alternatives of DLT solutions tested and evaluated.	At least 3 Open-Source solutions.
DLT-KPI-2	Criteria considered in the evaluation and selection.	At least 9 criteria including private visibility, associated consensus type, supported programming language, expressiveness of the supported language, necessary computing resources, available documentation, size of its community and activity in its repositories.
DLT-KPI-3	Interfaces provided to operate the Marketplace on top of a DLT infrastructure.	At least 3 Open-APIs for mediation between other sub-components and the DLT networks.
DLT-KPI-4	System to control the access based on identities.	Telematic access to the APIs controlled by a mechanism of tokens or DIDs and credentials.
DLT-KPI-11	Administrators of the Marketplace performing administration and governance operations.	At least 1 operator initiating the Marketplace platform.

DLT-KPI-13	Number of subcomponents interacting with the identity API answering to different needs through the same API.	At least 2 subcomponents accessing identity APIs, to verify stakeholder credentials, generate DIDs for offers, orders, etc. and retrieve DIDs associated to the stakeholder.
DLT-KPI-14	System administrating credentials and identifiers.	1 Identifier technology for different actors based on DID technologies supported by DLT.
DLT-KPI-15	Interconnection of infrastructures and domains.	1 VPN system to interconnect DLT nodes according to the IDs provided to each Operator.
DLT-KPI-16	Scalable in concurrency of actors.	1, 2 and 4 actors are possible without any manual intervention and without the need to scale the solution.
DLT-KPI-17	Scalable in offered networks concurrently.	A guide including the installation of the DLT node and the tests to check it is properly connected is provided.
DLT-KPI-19	Documentation of all repositories including deployment procedure and runtime use.	Repository for each block developed including the automatic deployment scripts and guided configuration.
DLT-KPI-20	Supported network configurations.	DLT solution tested in at least 2 different environments operating 2 different networks or deployed on one of them.
DLT-KPI-21	Estimate CAPEX and OPEX to support the definition of the business model.	Report required processing for all the systems along the tests.
DLT-KPI-22	Installation and configuration of SW pieces to adhere a new infrastructure.	Less than 10 minutes over the time to download online repositories.
SC System		
SC-KPI-2	The output of the SC State Composer shall be a json payload containing all the defined information.	Compliance with the schema of the Smart Contract state that will be defined.
SC-KPI-5	The SC State Composer will be deployed as a containerised application in K8s using Helm.	Helm chart syntax verification.
SC-KPI-6	The SC State Composer will be a stateless application.	No data volumes will be used.
SC-KPI-7	SC State Composer will be exposed using a REST API consumed over HTTP(s).	Compliance with the Open API specification.
SC-KPI-8	SC State Composer will consume the DLT functionalities using a REST API consumed over HTTP(s).	Success to communicate with the DLT layer of the project.
SD System		
SD-KPI-2	Number of offers per category included in the training dataset.	Minimum number of offers in the training dataset = 2k
SD-KPI-3	Performance of the clustering model measured by the Sum of Squared Errors (SSE).	SSE (clustering) converges to a value close to zero
SD-KPI-4	Accuracy of the classification model measured by the log loss.	Log loss (classification) <= 1
SD-KPI-5	Accuracy of the intent-based processing measured by the translation (comprehension) error.	Translation error (NLP) <= 10%

SD-KPI-7	Time consumed by tasks related to the pre-processing of the data before being used by the ML models.	Average data pre-processing time $\leq$ 5 mins
SD-KPI-8	Time consumed by training the clustering model.	Average training time (clustering) $\leq$ 100 secs
SD-KPI-9	Time consumed by training the classification model.	Average training time (classification) $\leq$ 50 secs
SD-KPI-13	Admissible increase in the training time given an increase in the training dataset.	Increase in the training time $\leq$ 10%
SD-KPI-14	Admissible reduction in the accuracy given a reduction in the number of pre-computed clusters per offer category.	Reduction in accuracy $\leq$ 5%
SLA Assurance System		
SLA-KPI-2	Namespace structure to facilitate local and global performance analysis.	At least 3 structures to differentiate radio, core and MEC resources in a network slice.
SLA-KPI-4	Different consumption modes for processing data.	Compatible with batch and live data consumption.
SLA-KPI-6	Different filters supported to enable granular focus on local slices and global focus on E2E slices.	At least 4 filters to select an E2E slice, the individual metrics before being aggregated from a local slice, a segment in a slice and a specific metric.
SLA-KPI-7	Number of asset types able to control.	Mapping RAN, core and edge controllers from different networks segments.
SLA-KPI-8	Number of topics and message types able to produce.	At least 2 topics for SLA breach and for assets deployment including the order and the status.
SLA-KPI-9	Support to produce and consume event streaming messages.	At least 3 message types for SLA breach information and for asset deployment including the order and the status parameters.
SLA-KPI-15	Scalable in concurrency of actors.	1, 2 and 4 actors are possible without any manual intervention and without the need to scale the solution.
SLA-KPI-16	Scalable in offered networks concurrently.	A guide including the installation of the SLA assurance system and the tests to check it is properly connected is provided.
SLA-KPI-17	Versatility in supported network configurations.	At least tested in 2 different environments operating 2 different networks or deployed on one of them.
SLA-KPI-18	Documentation of all repositories including deployment procedure and runtime use.	Repository for each block developed including the automatic deployment scripts and guided configuration.
SLA-KPI-19	Estimate CAPEX and OPEX to support the definition of the business model.	Report required processing for all the systems along the tests.

4.2 Use Case Validation KPIs

In contrast, the use case validation KPIs, also stemming from E2.1 [1], establish a direct correlation between the identified metrics and the validation of specific UC scenarios within the 6GENABLERS-DLT project. These KPIs, grouped in Table 4-2, highlight those performance metrics that directly influence and contribute to the success of use case tests. They reflect the dynamic interplay between platform capabilities and real-world

scenarios, offering a targeted evaluation of the platform's effectiveness in facilitating multi-party real-time holographic communications.

Table 4-2 Use Case Validation KPIs

ID	Description	Evaluation Criteria	Related UC Scenario
DLT System			
DLT-KPI-5	Registered offers submitted by stakeholders owning telco assets.	At least 1 offer registered for each stakeholder owning and operating telco assets.	Joint result of scenarios 1 – 4
DLT-KPI-6	Orders requested and simultaneously active.	At least 1 order requested for 1 XR Holoportation service consuming network and virtualisation resources.	Scenarios 1 – 3
DLT-KPI-7	Number of networks with assets involved in active smart contract orders.	At least 2 networks connected in an order providing an XR Holoportation service.	Scenario 4
DLT-KPI-8	SLA breaches registered in the Marketplace requiring notification and mediation.	At least 2 violations producing 2 new immediate registrations. 1 local in 1 of the networks and 1 global in 2 networks.	Scenarios 2 – 4
DLT-KPI-9	Number of networks providing offers, managing orders and hosting a DLT node.	At least 2 networks offering resources.	Scenarios 2 – 4
DLT-KPI-10	Number of consumers requesting for assets in the networks and ordering smart contracts.	At least 1 XR Holoportation service consuming network and virtualisation resources.	Scenarios 1 – 3
DLT-KPI-12	Number of actors present in the DLT-based Marketplace.	At least 5 types of actors (VSPs, MNOs, Infrastructure Providers, VSVs and VSCs).	Joint result of scenarios 1 – 4
DLT-KPI-18	Registration time in the DLT system.	Less than 1 second.	Measured for every scenario (1 – 4)
SC System			
SC-KPI-1	Local catalogue deployed with the SC State Composer to execute the filling out of templates and its rendering.	Success in executing an E2E experiment.	Measured for every scenario (1 – 4)
SC-KPI-3	A single VNF is expected to be offered using different business models in a B2B transaction. Then, it will be reused as part of an NS offer which is also expected to be offered using different business models in a B2C transaction.	Multiple offers publication in the Marketplace for VNFs and NSs.	Scenarios 1 and 4
SC-KPI-4	The E2E time that the SC State Composer takes to generate the final rendered document.	Rendering Time <=2 seconds	Measured for every scenario (1 – 4)
SC-KPI-9	The E2E time that it takes for the SC state to be published in the DLT.	DLT Interaction Time <= 5 seconds	Measured for every scenario (1 – 4)

SD System			
SD-KPI-1	Number of offer categories supported by the Smart Discovery models	Minimum number of supported categories = 5	Joint result of scenarios 1 – 4, plus additional categories to be reported.
SD-KPI-6	Divergence between the requirements set in the intent and the returned offers.	Total error (NLP) <= 30%	Measured for every scenario (1 – 4)
SD-KPI-10	Time consumed by classifying an incoming offer, i.e., to determine the cluster to which the offer corresponds.	Average inference time (classification) <= 5 secs	Measured for every scenario (1 – 4)
SD-KPI-11	Time consumed by processing an intent request, i.e., to translate the intent into the appropriate cluster(s).	Average inference time (NLP) <= 2 secs	Measured for every scenario (1 – 4)
SD-KPI-12	Speed at which the Smart Discovery system processes user intents and provides the corresponding list of offers.	Average discovery time <= 5 secs	Measured for every scenario (1 – 4)
SLA Assurance System			
SLA-KPI-1	Different metrics from different network segments.	At least 10 metrics being captured and aggregated from different segments and networks.	Joint result of scenarios 2 – 4
SLA-KPI-3	Number of networks producing data to the monitoring system.	At least 2 networks involved in an order and providing metrics.	Scenario 4
SLA-KPI-5	Number of installations of the SLA assurance system.	At least 1 stakeholder making use of the SLA assurance system.	Scenarios 2 – 4
SLA-KPI-10	Control for all segments in a network slice.	At least 3 mapped API interfaced controllers of RAN, core and edge controllers.	Scenario 3
SLA-KPI-11	Report on deployment feedback.	At least an update every 30 secs.	Measured for every scenario (2 – 4)
SLA-KPI-12	Time to deliver all the requests to local controllers.	Complete a deployment in less than 10 minutes.	Measured for every scenario (2 – 4)
SLA-KPI-13	Interconnection of multiple infrastructures and domains.	At least 2 administrative networks.	Scenario 4
SLA-KPI-14	Testing providing network assets for XR Holoportation services.	At least 2 holoportation users each on 1 operated network. A maximum of 4 holoportation users on a maximum of 3 networks.	Scenario 4

5 Deployment and Validation Environment

The deployment and validation environment for the 6GENABLERS-DLT project serves as the foundational infrastructure for hosting the Marketplace platform, accompanied by the underlying DLT nodes. This environment, depicted in Figure 5-1, is meticulously designed to accommodate a multi-party network of independent and mutually untrusting Marketplace stakeholders, providing a dynamic and realistic setting for thorough validation.

Figure 5-1 Deployment and Validation Environment

This experimental environment acts as the central hosting environment for the 6GENABLERS Marketplace platform and associated DLT nodes. It serves as the interconnected ecosystem where stakeholders, each operating independently, collaboratively engage in multi-party transactions.

As illustrated in Figure 5-1, the testbed provisioned at i2CAT premises emulates a multi-party network comprising diverse and independent Marketplace stakeholders. Stakeholders within this network operate autonomously, fostering an environment of mutual distrust, mirroring real-world scenarios and challenges. The visual representation illustrates the hierarchical structure of the 6GENABLERS-DLT deployment and validation environment, showcasing the interplay between multiple stakeholders, the underlying DLT network, and the infrastructure sustainment through Kubernetes clusters.

- **Marketplace Services:** The uppermost layer of the figure encapsulates the diverse ecosystem of stakeholders, each hosting and operating their individual instances of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. These stakeholders, representing

various actors within the 6G landscape, actively engage with the platform to consume its services, fostering collaboration and resource sharing.

- **DLT Network:** The middle layer of the figure symbolizes the intricate web of cross-domain connectivity and data-sharing mechanisms facilitated by the DLT network. This network serves as the backbone for the seamless operation of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, enabling secure and transparent transactions among stakeholders. The interconnected mesh highlights the dynamic exchange of data and transactions within this decentralized environment.
- **Infrastructure:** At the infrastructure level, the platform finds its support in provisioned Kubernetes clusters. These clusters form the robust foundation upon which the 6GENABLERS Marketplace operates. Kubernetes, renowned for its container orchestration capabilities, ensures the scalability, manageability, and resilience of the platform's underlying infrastructure.

The setup required to isolate different stakeholder spaces is a critical consideration. This isolation is achieved through the provisioning of different namespaces over a single Kubernetes cluster or the interconnection of multiple bare-metal clusters. This strategic implementation ensures that each stakeholder operates within a segregated environment, fostering autonomy and security.

Additionally, the deployment and validation environment offers flexibility to extend its reach by adding other peers, hosted by the organizations involved in the project. In particular, an extension is proposed to incorporate Vicomtech premises. This extension involves the addition of another peer within Vicomtech, contributing to the overall multi-party network. This extension enhances the diversity and complexity of the network, allowing for a more comprehensive evaluation of the 6GENABLERS-DLT platform.

The purpose of the deployment and validation environment is multi-directional. The primary objective is to validate the proper integration among the different developed components of the 6GENABLERS-DLT platform. The testbed provides a controlled environment to assess the seamless interaction between the Marketplace platform and the underlying DLT nodes.

Additionally, it provides an ideal experimental environment to evaluate the operational aspects of the DLT deployment within the testbed. This testbed will be used to assess the reliability, fault tolerance, and performance of the DLT nodes under real-world conditions.

Finally, the testbed will be fundamental to validate the deployment of the conceived use case scenarios to demonstrate the platform's capabilities to unlock collaboration and resource sharing for the establishment of real-time holographic communications. Likewise, it will be used to conduct a comprehensive evaluation of the Marketplace performance, focusing on technical KPIs.

6 Conclusion

This deliverable represents a significant milestone within the 6GENABLERS-DLT project, providing a comprehensive framework for validating the innovative Marketplace. This conclusion synthesizes key insights and takeaways derived from the detailed validation methodology and performance analysis plan outlined in the document.

The systematic approach presented in Section 2 emphasizes the importance of aligning validation objectives with project activities, setting the stage for effective testing and evaluation. The validation objectives and scope, as outlined in Section 2.1, provide a clear understanding of the overarching goals, ensuring that the 6GENABLERS Marketplace meets its intended objectives. The approach and procedures detailed in Section 2.2 offer a roadmap, starting from the initial definition of use cases and KPIs to the final validation and performance analysis.

Moving to Section 3, the use case validation, the document delves into specific test cases and scenarios for the Marketplace. Each test case, from stakeholder onboarding to SLA violation notification and registration, is meticulously detailed to capture the nuances of the platform's functionality. The associated tables succinctly summarize the main aspects of each operation, providing a quick reference for stakeholders involved in the validation process.

In Section 4, the performance analysis plan, the focus shifts to the identification and measurement of KPIs. The differentiation between platform capabilities KPIs and use case validation KPIs allows for a targeted approach, ensuring that both the broader platform capabilities and the specific use case scenarios are thoroughly evaluated. This section forms a critical component of the overall validation strategy, emphasizing the importance of technical KPIs in assessing the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

Section 5 addresses the deployment and validation environment, outlining the testbed's characteristics and requirements. This section provides insights into the multi-party network of independent stakeholders and the infrastructure required to support realistic testing scenarios.

In conclusion, this deliverable provides not only a roadmap for validating the 6GENABLERS Marketplace but also serves as a reference for stakeholders involved in the project. The validation methodology and performance analysis plan laid out herein establish the foundation for ongoing efforts, ensuring the successful deployment and optimization of the distributed telco Marketplace within the dynamic landscape of 6G environments. As the project advances, the methodologies presented in this document will continue to guide the effective validation and refinement of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

7 References

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